

A CHANGE FROM CLASSROOM TO DISTANCE

LEARNING : PLUSES AND RESTRICTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article considers betterment of technology, the demand for teaching ways of education. Distance education, which is difference from tradition learning, the convenience offers by studying online transcending limitation time and place. Both learning techniques have their advantages and disadvantages. The benefits of the researcher goals to discuss history and opportunity of distance learning, literature of distance learning, express of the study to learners and teachers. Differences between face to face and online learning, which studying from home where learners and teachers are physically distant whereas classroom learning in which the learners and teachers work under one roof.

KEY WORDS: distance learning, education, history, advantages and disadvantages, teachers, students.

INTRODUCTION

Distance learning has become an important part of the educational world, where students gain instruction through online classes, video recordings, or other technology. It enables people to take education without having to be physically present in a classroom. Distance learning programs can be convenient to obtain more education. Distance learning today takes place using the Internet, readily approachable for the majority learners in their homes or at facilities. Distance

learning can use other technological ways such as television, DVDs and printable materials. Online programs rarely receive plus of a number of appearing technologies to make keeping in touch and efficiently communicating ideas and more effectively than before and students find themselves using conversational videos and lessons [Velasenko and Bozhok, 2014].

HISTORY OF DISTANCE LEARNING

Although now there are has been discharge of distance learning , especially due to the new technologies available, the origin of distance education can traced back to about 100 years ago (Birnbaum 2001, Hanson et al 1997). These types of consignment methods and media used as distance learning began to grow as a form of education. Early distance education courses worked first and second generation communication technologies. First generation (1850 to 1960) was technology and include of print and radio and television. Second generation (1960 to 1985) distance education uses multiple technologies without computers. Moore (1990) sees the success of distance education the satisfy of the dialog between teacher and student and the benefit of the communication system in an educational process.

EVIDENCES OF DISTANCE LEARNING EFFECTIVESS

Distance education is similar to a traditional form of education has been a debated topic, large amounts of previously unreachable information, research has made paces in studying the interaction between educational and distance learning technologies[2,2].Distance learning courses should be carefully designed for specific aims and developed before the start of the course. It is significant to use ways to visualize ideas and theories to be provided to distance learners.

ADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE LEARNING

Distance education is the best choice for every student to pursue a school and university program. Distance education might learn it from anywhere and at any time. Even if your course is provided by an international school and university and students could get receive to course material if student are a citizen a another nation. The fee of a distance education degree may more accessible than the fee of often get degree. Students are looking for economically ideas can go for a distance education program. Students can study wherever they have entrance to a computer and internet. The course offered a distance learning centers are cheaper than the courses attended at traditional learning centers[Brown 2017]. Learners will have to follow a begin schedule of learning the timetable of the school if they are following traditional program of learning. Many types of distance education permit learners to set learning schedule as their comfort without a regular timetable of learning. Distance learning program offers them convenience to study their course learning. There's no time wasted in going to and from school and university, no time wasted waiting for a bus or taxi. In a distance learning program, your classroom is right in their room and the study material on their desk and the email.

DISADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE LEARNING

Distance learning provides more people opportunity to attain higher education. There are no faculty around for face to face with classmates who can help with persistent reminders about undecided assignments. Students need to keep yourself motivated and focused if they want to complete their distance learning course. If student have any hesitation then they have to clear yourself without taking help from their teacher and friends and they can not talk to friends and other classmates that they do in college course. Any student look for enroll for a distance education program needs to fund in a variety of equipment consist of computer and webcam. Learners will often be studying solely and they miss the social physical interaction that attend a traditional classroom. The lack of physical relation in the educational

process may cause problems, including degree of blazing and isolation. Distance learning limits students to classes and learning materials are based online. Learners have trouble with assignments or questions about theme whereas in a traditional class it is common simple to talk to the instructor before or after classroom and timetable meetings online at any time.

THE METHOD OF STUDY BOTH TEACHERS AND LEARNERS

The new generation is close with technology so they won't be satisfied with traditional methods of learning. Many opportunity can be used to help them learn effectively. They learn using many materials and online courses that are designed for active learning. Many types of teaching helps instructors to teach at home and begin their own teaching hours. Teachers access their virtual educate session from computers anywhere in the world. Learners apply any type of distance learning program, they had better carefully consider these actions in order to be sure they will be getting an education that meets strengths, career , goals.

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